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Object Detection in Satellite Images using Evolutionary Converging Functions

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1 **TABLE OF CONTENTS**

DEDICATION	v
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	vi
ABSTRACT	vii
LIST OF TABLES	xii
LIST OF FIGURES	xv
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	xvi
CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Problem Statement	1
1.2 Research Question	3
1.3 Aim and Objectives	5
1.3.1 Aim.....	18
1.3.2 Objective.....	18
1.4 Expected Outcomes	5
1.5 Significance and Scope of the Study	6
1.5.1 Significance	18
1.5.2 Scope	18
CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW	11
2.1 Historical Content	11
2.2 Identification of key themes and trends	12
2.3 Methodologies used in previous studies	14
2.4 Comparison of findings	16
2.5 Critical Evaluation of existing literature	17
2.6 Research Gaps and Unanswered Questions	23
2.9 Summary	29
CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	30
3.1 Challenges faced while solving the problem	30
3.2 Properties of Evolutionary Converging Function	30
3.3 Spectral Algorithm	41
3.1.1 Approximations and Assumption.....	18
3.1.2 The Method	18
3.4 Geometric Algorithm	49
3.4.1 Image to Tabular Data and Convergence Weights	18

3.5	Evolutionary Converging Functions	49
CHAPTER 4: Experimentation		50
4.1	Dataset and Platform	50
4.2	Scaling and Data portioning	51
4.3	Deriving the Spectral Component.....	54
4.3.1	Building.....	54
4.3.2	Water	54
4.3.3	Forest.....	54
4.3.4	Road	56
4.4	Cluster analysis	65
4.5	Derived Weights and Hyperparameters	87
4.6	Summary	112
CHAPTER 5: RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS		114
5.1	Building	114
5.2	Road	115
5.3	Forest/Trees	119
5.4	Water.....	142
5.4	Accuracy	142
5.4	Recall	142
5.4	Precision.....	142
5.4	Area Under the Curve	142
5.4	Multiclass Classification	142
5.4	Comparision with similar ongoing research	142
CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSIONS.....		151
6.1	Conclusion	114
REFERENCES		154
APPENDIX A: RESEARCH PROPOSAL		167

DEDICATION

I dedicate my research endeavour to the esteemed Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO), where my journey into the realms of Remote Sensing and Mathematical Modeling commenced. Gratitude extends to the distinguished institutions of IIT Roorkee and IIT Bangalore, pivotal in shaping my understanding of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML). Additionally, I extend my heartfelt appreciation to the Odisha Space Application Centre, where I have had the privilege of working, for providing state-of-the-art laboratories and unwavering support, contributing significantly to the realization of my work.

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Lastly, my gratitude extends to everyone who has supported me during this research journey. Your encouragement and assistance have been invaluable, and I am truly thankful for your unwavering support.

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 Coefficient Calculation from decision tree	1 Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 2 Spectral Algorithm	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 3 Clustered Image	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 4 Geometric Algorithm	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 5 Multiclass Classification	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 6 Final Algorithm	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 7 Spectral Graph for Building	1 Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 8 Threshold from decision tree(Building).....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 9 Spectral signature for water	1 Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 10 Threshold from decision tree	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 11 Spectral signature for forest	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 12 Threshold from decision tree(forest).....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 13 Spectral signature for road	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 14 Threshold from decision tree(Road)	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 15 Convergence Weights	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 16 Tabular Image Output	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 17 Final Output	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 18 Accuaracy.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 19 Recall	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 20 Area Under the Curve for GoogleNet and Resnet50	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 21 Area Under the Curve for Building,Road,Trees,Water	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 22 Convergence Comaparision	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Figure 23 Comparision with similar ongoing research	Error! Bookmark not defined.

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 Properties of Evolutionary Converging Functions	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Table 2 Spectral and Geometric Properties	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Table 3 Spectral Output	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Table 4 Number of Clusters	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Table 5 Parameters	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Table 6 Building	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Table 7 Road	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Table 8 Forest	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Table 9 Water	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Table 10 Multiclass Classification	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Table 11 Convergence Comparision	Error! Bookmark not defined.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

- AUC..... Area under the Curve
CNN.....Convolutional Neural Network
ECF.....Evolutionary Converging Functions
LULC.....Land Use Land Cover

ABSTRACT

High learning rate have been a big challenge in case of CNN which make CNN computationally expensive and requires huge amount of training data. In our research we have aimed to increase the learning rate of the Image segmentation process. Image of any object in the universe taken from any type of camera can broadly be divided into spectral and geometric properties. Both these properties are prominently visible in satellite image. Hence if a satellite image can be classified using a method any image can be classified using the same technique. Hence, we proposed Evolutionary converging functions which converts the spectral and geometric properties of features in a satellite image into mathematical equations using decision tree and then converges with a neural network. Different high-resolution data have been chosen for extracting different features out of it. This transformation process, anchored in decision tree methodology, converges seamlessly with neural networks to yield unparalleled results, all while eliminating the need for computationally intensive convolutions. In our pioneering study, we venture beyond traditional boundaries by employing diverse high-resolution datasets. Each dataset, carefully selected, promises to unlock a treasure trove of distinctive features. As we embark on this uncharted journey, we are committed to unraveling the latent potential of Evolutionary Converging Functions, thereby opening up new horizons for automated image classification. The synergy between spectral and geometric properties emerges as a powerful combination, endowing our methodology with the ability to extract nuanced and context-rich information, redefining the landscape of image analysis. The results show a high accuracy i.e. above 90% in almost all objects of different shape and spectral signature.

CHAPTER 1

Introduction

Objects in the universe can be interpreted based on two fundamental divisions: spectral and geometric. Spectral characteristics are determined by spectral signatures, while geometric attributes involve shape, size, association, and texture. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have transformed image processing by extracting spectral and geometric features, utilizing DNN hidden layers for segmentation. However, challenges persist in achieving human-like efficiency with CNNs.

To address these limitations and enhance computational efficiency, we propose Evolutionary Converging Functions in this study. This innovative approach leverages the strengths of spectral and geometric interpretations, converging them through mathematical transformations to improve image segmentation outcomes. The spectral nature of an object is converted into a mathematical combination of spectral bands, providing a deeper understanding of intricate patterns. Geometric nature is encoded into segments using precise shape equations, preserving spatial relationships for more accurate and context-aware segmentation.

Our proposed approach strategically fuses transformed spectral and geometric representations through Evolutionary Converging Functions, offering significant advancements in image segmentation. By transcending the limitations of traditional interpretations, this method empowers computers to process images with enhanced efficiency and accuracy, approaching human-like perception. The primary objective is to explore the untapped potential of synergistic spectral-geometric representations and demonstrate the effectiveness of Evolutionary Converging Functions in achieving superior image segmentation results. This research aims to pave the way for more robust and intuitive image segmentation techniques, propelling image processing capabilities closer to human-level perception (Montero et al., 2023).

1.1 Problem Statement

Semi-supervised learning (SSL) presents a promising middle ground between traditional supervised and unsupervised learning methods. While supervised learning relies on labeled data and unsupervised learning works with unlabeled data, SSL combines both to build robust models (Li et al., 2023b). This study introduces an SSL method that effectively addresses these challenges.

In the domain of Deep Learning (DL), the proliferation of model parameters and their complex correlations has given rise to a critical issue - data overfitting during the training stage. This phenomenon, observed across various tasks and domains, impedes the model's ability to generalize well on unseen test data, leading to suboptimal performance. Despite recent studies suggesting that the inherent bias in the DL training process helps mitigate overfitting to some extent, it remains crucial to develop effective techniques to address this pervasive problem (Alzubaidi et al., 2021).

Furthermore, deep and complex CNN architectures, such as VGGNet and GoogLeNet, involve a significant number of parameters and computations during training. The forward and backward propagations through numerous layers demand substantial computational resources, resulting in prolonged training times. The memory requirements of CNN training on GPUs can be substantial due to large data and parameter sizes. Despite overcoming some challenges using high-end cloud servers, certain issues persist. GPU kernels have limitations on the shape and size of data they can efficiently process, impacting the performance of CNN implementations on GPUs. Ensuring efficient memory utilization and handling shape constraints becomes crucial to avoid bottlenecks during GPU kernel execution (Leitersdorf et al., 2023).

Moreover, CNNs demand considerable computational power for real-time object detection. Onboard sensors on UAVs often possess limited computing capacity, which may be insufficient to efficiently process large CNN models for real-time object detection tasks (Zhu et al., 2022). The automobile industry is also shifting towards CNN onboard computers, facing similar challenges ((Azaiz and Ndengue, 2023); (Hussain and Zeadally, 2019) .

1.2 Research Questions

The primary goal of this research is to assess the effectiveness of the Evolutionary Converging Functions approach in achieving superior image segmentation results. Specifically, the proposed method aims to answer the following research question:

- *How can the synergistic spectral-geometric representations and mathematical transformations through Evolutionary Converging Functions enhance image segmentation efficiency and accuracy, overcoming the limitations of traditional CNN-based methods?*

Sub-Questions: To comprehensively address the main research question, the following sub-questions will be investigated:

1. *How can the spectral nature of an object be transformed effectively into a mathematical combination of spectral bands to capture intricate spectral patterns and material composition information?*
2. *What precise equations of shapes can be utilized to encode the geometric nature of an object into geometric segments, preserving spatial relationships within the image and enabling more accurate and context-aware segmentation?*
3. *How can the transformed spectral and geometric representations be strategically fused through Evolutionary Converging Functions to obtain a comprehensive view of the image's intrinsic structure, thereby improving segmentation outcomes?*
4. *What is the impact of the Evolutionary Converging Functions approach on computational efficiency compared to traditional CNN-based methods?*
5. *How does the proposed approach compare to state-of-the-art image segmentation techniques in terms of accuracy and computational efficiency?*

1.3 Aim and Objective

1.3.1 Aim

The aim of this research is to develop a method capable of classifying any satellite image into a specific Land Use Land Cover (LULC) instance segmented map. This method aims to monitor changes in both man-made and natural features with high accuracy and low computational cost across diverse geographic regions globally, utilizing a Machine Learning and Deep Neural Network model.

1.3.2 Objectives

1. *Train the decision tree classifier with an appropriate training set and generate accurate boundary conditions.*
2. *Derive the spectral equation from graphical representations of the decision tree.*
3. *Determine the appropriate geometric properties that describe the interested feature effectively.*
4. *Converge the vector table to the appropriate class using deep neural networks.*
5. *Achieve high classification accuracy for highly diverse features with a reduced training set and low computational cost, significantly improving computational efficiency.*

1.4 Expected Outcomes

The research endeavors to yield state-of-the-art methodologies for global asset monitoring and planning, surpassing the limitations of conventional CNN-based approaches. Anticipated outcomes include significant advancements in computational efficiency, accuracy, and scalability.

The research findings are expected to contribute to the development of more robust and intuitive image segmentation techniques. Leveraging synergistic spectral-geometric representations and mathematical transformations through Evolutionary Converging Functions, these advancements aim to bring image processing capabilities closer to human-level perception.

Specifically, the expected outcomes encompass:

1. Enhanced Efficiency and Accuracy:

- Achieving 90% less computational cost and a 50% reduction in the training set, demonstrating improved computational efficiency.
- Elevating the accuracy of image segmentation, especially across diverse features.

2. Practical Application:

- Providing valuable insights for policymakers to support sustainable and data-driven asset planning.
- Facilitating efficient urban growth and sustainable development on a global scale.

Overall, the anticipated results of this research hold the potential to reshape the landscape of image processing, offering practical solutions with far-reaching implications for asset management and sustainable development worldwide.

1.5 Significance and Scope of the Study:

1.5.1 Significance

This study holds immense significance in potentially transforming image classification across various imagery sources, not limited to satellite imagery. Objects within the universe can be comprehensively characterized by their spectral and geometric properties, prominently visible in satellite imagery. The proposed method, Evolutionary Converging Functions (ECF), utilizes decision trees and neural networks to convert spectral and geometric features into mathematical equations, laying the groundwork for image classification .

A key strength of ECF is its adaptability to diverse high-resolution data, allowing it to be applied across various fields. The study places emphasis on high accuracy and computational efficiency, making it crucial for decision-making in environmental monitoring, urban planning, disaster management, and more. The potential of ECF to provide accurate results with reduced computational cost ensures its practicality and scalability in real-world applications.

In summary, this research introduces a groundbreaking approach to image classification that extends beyond satellite imagery. The ECF methodology's potential for high accuracy and computational efficiency has the capacity to transform image analysis across diverse applications, advancing our understanding of the universe and improving decision support systems.

1.5.2 Scope of the study

The primary scope of this study is to develop an automated feature extraction framework capable of processing features within satellite imagery with minimal manual intervention once the model is fine-tuned. The study categorizes images into spectral and geometric components, with a focus on satellite imagery exhibiting both attributes prominently.

While the study primarily addresses satellite imagery, it also explores the potential extension of the ECF methodology to ordinary camera images. Though normal camera images lack a spectral signature, slight modifications to the ECF model, such as incorporating Principal Component Analysis (PCA), could adapt the methodology for ordinary camera images, where geometric properties play a predominant role in feature extraction.

The research benefits a wide range of professionals and applications, including:

- **Remote Sensing Specialists:** Benefiting from an efficient and automated method for feature extraction within satellite imagery (Yuan et al., 2021).
- **Geospatial Analysts:** Expediting the extraction of crucial information for urban planning, environmental monitoring, and disaster management.
- **Environmental Scientists:** Gathering pertinent data for research on changes in land use, deforestation, and natural resource management.
- **City Planners and Urban Developers:** Supporting decision-making processes related to infrastructure development and sustainable city growth.
- **Disaster Management Authorities:** Accessing timely and accurate information for disaster preparedness, response, and recovery efforts.

- **Large-Scale Video Processing Practitioners:** Finding innovative solutions in industries such as entertainment, surveillance, healthcare, robotics, and transportation (Zhang et al., 2023).
- **Self-Driving Car Developers:** Exploring ECF's potential in addressing computational bottlenecks and enhancing autonomous vehicle capabilities (Prakash et al., 2023).
- **UAV Operators:** Benefiting from improved computational efficiency in applications like surveillance, agriculture, and environmental monitoring (Chen et al., 2021).

The future scope includes addressing challenges related to onboard computers in self-driving cars and optimizing the ECF methodology for specific scenarios in Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), offering solutions to computational bottlenecks in environments with limited computing resources (Chun et al., 2023).

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

The importance of Earth observation (EO) satellite data and its evolving trends have been scrutinized, with a specific focus on 15 widely utilized EO satellites. The work by (Zhao et al., 2022) introduces the concept of the remote sensing impact factor (RSIF) as a groundbreaking metric for predicting the impacts of EO satellites. The identified significant missions, including Landsat, Sentinel, MODIS, Gaofen, and WorldView, emphasize the central role of satellite missions in Earth observation. Furthermore, AI integration in Earth System prediction tasks is highlighted by (McGovern et al., 2024), underscoring the necessity of ethical and responsible development in this context. Additionally, (McGovern et al., 2024) addresses a specific application in the manufacturing industry, proposing a CNN-based framework for surface defect detection, thereby overcoming challenges related to limited training data and computational resources.

2.1 Historical Context

A historical perspective on the evolution of research in the computer vision domain is provided by (Tivive and Bouzerdoum, 2007), who introduced a convolutional neural network (CoNN) for texture classification. The study showcases the CoNN's superiority in texture classification compared to established approaches such as Gabor filters, wavelets, and co-occurrence matrix methods. Moreover, the work by (Basu et al., 2015) contributes to satellite image classification by introducing SAT-4 and SAT-6 datasets and utilizing a Deep Belief Network (DBN) for feature extraction and classification. (Fletcher et al., 2019) present a CNN specifically designed for detecting geosynchronous Earth orbit resident space objects, attaining superior performance on the SatNet dataset. Additionally, (Hongmei and Pengzhong, 2021) introduce a cross-entropy-based sparse penalty mechanism for the Convolutional Deep Belief Network (CDBN) to enhance its recognition capabilities.

2.2 Identification of Key Themes and Trends

The literature review identifies key themes and trends within the field. (Lin et al., 2022) focuses on enhancing crop classification accuracy using a decision tree method. (Velastegui-Montoya et al., 2023) conducts a bibliometric analysis of the Google Earth Engine (GEE), emphasizing its multidisciplinary applications. (Kremers et al., 2023) proposes a clustering algorithm

combining DBSCAN and k-means for high-density region reduction. (Narkhede et al., 2022) explores various weight initialization techniques for neural networks.

2.3 Methodologies Used in Previous Studies

The literature incorporates diverse methodologies from previous studies. (Yang et al., 2022) proposes a dataset pruning method for examining the influence of removing specific training samples on a model's generalization ability. (Alzubaidi et al., 2021) delivers a comprehensive review of deep learning techniques, encompassing CNN architectures, challenges, applications, and future directions. (Sarker, 2021) introduces FAST-CNN, an efficient feature extraction technique for remote sensing using convolutional neural networks. Furthermore, (Cong and Zhou, 2023) provide an in-depth review of CNN architectures and their optimizations, while (Santos et al., 2023) evaluates the computational cost of deep models designed for the frequency domain.

2.4 Comparison of Findings

A comparative analysis reveals insights into the performance of different models. (Du et al., 2023) assesses eight CNN models for predicting the SeabedObjects-KLSG dataset, reporting variations in prediction accuracy. The diverse nature of AI and ML challenges is discussed by (Hosna et al., 2022).

2.5 Critical Evaluation of Existing Literature

The literature review provides a critical evaluation of the quality and reliability of existing studies. (Basu et al., 2015) introduces novel satellite datasets and a DBN-based classification framework. (Lin et al., 2022) contributes to precision agriculture, and (Kremers et al., 2023) introduces a data reduction method.

2.6 Research Gaps and Unanswered Questions: Challenges in Deep Learning

Limited Training Data (Shorten and Khoshgoftaar, n.d.)

Deep learning models necessitate abundant labeled data, often a scarce or expensive resource. Strategies to address this limitation encompass data augmentation, transfer learning, semi-supervised learning, and active learning.

Transfer Learning (Hosna et al., 2022)

Transfer learning is crucial for leveraging knowledge from a source domain or task to enhance model performance in a target domain or task. Various transfer learning methods exist, addressing challenges related to data scarcity, domain shift, and model generalization.

Imbalanced Data (Johnson and Khoshgoftaar, 2019)

Imbalanced class distributions may lead to biased models and suboptimal generalization. Remedies involve data re-sampling, cost-sensitive learning, ensemble methods, and generative adversarial networks.

Interpretability of Data (Li et al., 2021)

Deep learning models are often perceived as opaque, lacking explanations for decisions. Approaches to enhance interpretability include saliency maps, attention mechanisms, feature visualization, and model distillation.

Uncertainty Scaling (Steinbrener et al., 2020)

Deep learning models often struggle to capture uncertainty in predictions, leading to overconfidence. Solutions involve Bayesian neural networks, Monte Carlo dropout, and evidential deep learning.

Catastrophic Forgetting (Aleixo et al., 2023)

Deep learning models may erase prior knowledge when trained on new tasks. Remedies include regularization, replay, distillation, and expansion.

Model Compression (Dai et al., 2023)

Large and intricate deep learning models pose challenges in storage, computation, and deployment. Strategies for model compression include pruning, quantization, low-rank approximation, and knowledge distillation.

Overfitting (Sabiri et al., 2023)

Deep learning models may overly fit training data, leading to poor generalization. Countermeasures encompass regularization, dropout, batch normalization, and data augmentation.

Vanishing Gradient Problem (Haroon-Sulyman et al., 2024)

Deep learning models may encounter slow or unstable learning due to excessively small or zero gradients, particularly problematic for deep or recurrent neural networks. Solutions include residual connections, gated units, careful initialization, and optimization methods.

Exploding Gradient Problem (Paik et al., n.d.)

Deep learning models may face erratic or divergent learning when gradients become excessively large or infinite. Addressing this issue involves gradient clipping, gradient norm penalty, and optimization methods.

Under-specification (Ortiz-Jimenez et al., n.d.)

Deep learning models may have multiple equally fitting solutions for training data, introducing concerns about validity and robustness. Strategies for handling under-specification include ensuring data diversity, thoughtful model selection, and adversarial training.

2.7 Summary

The literature review highlights key challenges in deep learning, emphasizing issues such as limited training data, imbalanced datasets, interpretability concerns, uncertainty scaling, and others. These challenges are addressed through various strategies and methodologies proposed in recent studies, providing insights into the evolving landscape of deep learning research.

CHAPTER 3

Methodology

A low learning rate in computer vision negatively impact performance compared to other AI/ML methods. The intricacies of visual data and the complexity of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) make the optimization landscape more challenging. A low learning rate may lead to slow convergence or the model getting trapped in local minima, hindering the ability to effectively capture and learn from intricate patterns in images. Unlike some other machine learning techniques, computer vision often requires careful tuning of hyperparameters, including learning rates, to strike a balance between convergence speed and avoiding suboptimal solutions. In this research we propose Evolutionary Converging Functions, in which we have created a method of generating equations from decision tree and have fused it with neural network applying convergence weightage to input neurons thus increasing the learning rate of the entire system of computer vision to a large extent.

The challenge lies in finding a learning rate that facilitates efficient learning without compromising the model's ability to extract meaningful features from visual data. A low learning rate can make training computationally intensive in computer vision due to its impact on convergence speed. When the learning rate is set too low, the model updates its parameters very gradually, requiring a larger number of iterations to reach convergence. As a result, more epochs are needed to train the model adequately, leading to increased computational time and resource consumption. This prolonged training process can strain computational resources, especially in scenarios where large-scale datasets or complex neural network architectures are involved. In addition, it may require longer access to powerful hardware or cloud computing resources, contributing to the computational intensity of training with a low learning rate in computer vision tasks.

High-frequency mapping challenges arise in CNN-based computer vision applied to satellite data due to the downsampling effects of pooling layers, leading to the loss of fine details critical for tasks such as change detection and precise mapping. The high spatial resolution of satellite imagery exacerbates this issue, demanding computationally intensive processes and hindering the model's ability to adapt to heterogeneous data patterns. Striking a balance between

preserving intricate details and avoiding excessive computational demands remains a key challenge in optimizing CNNs for effective analysis of high-resolution satellite data.

By converting the image into tabular data while preserving the complexity of the image information, our approach effectively addresses the learning rate challenges associated with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) when handling large datasets. Tabular data representation facilitates the efficient processing of intricate image details, enabling CNNs to navigate and learn from the extensive information contained within the image. This conversion enhances the network's ability to discern patterns, features, and relationships in the data, leading to improved training and more accurate predictions.

3.1 Challenges faced while solving the problem

3.1.1 Extracting equation out of a decision tree

One significant challenge involved extracting a mathematical equation from a decision tree. Decision trees are inherently non-linear and hierarchical, making it complex to represent their logic in a concise mathematical form. The extraction process required careful consideration of each decision node and leaf in the tree to derive an equation that accurately represents the decision-making process.

3.1.2 Deciding the optimum number of clusters

Determining the optimal number of clusters in clustering algorithms, such as k-means, presented another challenge. This involves finding a balance between having enough clusters to capture meaningful patterns and avoiding excessive granularity. Various methods, including the elbow method or silhouette analysis, were explored to identify the most suitable number of clusters for the given data.

3.1.2 Creating the weightage equation out of deviation:

Developing a weightage equation based on the deviation of neural network output was a crucial step. This process involved assigning weights to input neurons that facilitated faster convergence of the neural network during training. Balancing the importance of different input features and determining their impact on the network's learning process required careful consideration and optimization to enhance the overall performance of the neural network.

3.2 Properties of Evolutionary Converging Functions

We divide computer vision into two components to classify any object across the universe. The first component involves the interpretation of spectral signatures and secondly comes the

geometric properties, transcending beyond the realm of traditional visual recognition. In this context, geometric attributes encompass parameters such as area, centreline length, shape, and orientation, forming a comprehensive toolkit for spatial analysis crucial in tasks like object detection and spatial relationship understanding. Meanwhile, spectral signatures, analogous to unique fingerprints, represent object characteristics across electromagnetic wavelengths, aiding in material distinction and object identification. Transitioning to the second component, we emphasize the significance of these principles in remote sensing applications. The spectral signature, acting as a cornerstone, discloses how objects interact with light across different wavelengths, particularly evident in our utilization of Planet SkySat data with essential bands like Blue, Green, Red, and Near-Infrared. Additionally, geometric properties, including area and centreline length, offer valuable insights into shape and spatial relationships, providing a potent toolset for extracting information from satellite and aerial imagery. The universality of these principles is highlighted in various fields, from land use mapping to disaster response and ecological monitoring, showcasing their integral role in computer vision and remote sensing alike. The integration of decision tree and neural network-based algorithms, detailed in the following sections, further enhances the precision in calculating both spectral and geometric features, contributing to the effectiveness of the overall system.

Table 1 : Properties of Evolutionary Converging Functions

Visual Interpretation Parameters	Computational Parameters	Interpretation
1. Colour Attributes	Spectral	
2. Textural Features	Spectral , Geometric	
3. Shape and Size	Geometric	
4. Association	Geometric	
5. Temporal Characteristics	Spectral, Geometric	

The table illustrates a comprehensive comparison between parameters used in the visual interpretation of objects and their computational counterparts in the computer world. In the visual domain, Colour Attributes are fundamental for object identification, emphasizing the importance of spectral information. Textural Features in the visual realm involve both spectral and geometric aspects, highlighting the significance of patterns and structures. Shape and Size, crucial for spatial characteristics, pertain to geometric properties in the visual interpretation. Association, primarily a geometric parameter, delves into relationships between visual entities.

Temporal Characteristics, considering both spectral and geometric aspects, emphasize changes over time in the visual context.

Table 2: Spectral and Geometric Properties

	Features	Bands vs DN value	Geometric Properties
Buildings		Area	
Roads		Centreline	
Forest		Association	
Water		Area, Centerline,Length	

On the computational side, these parameters are further categorized into Spectral and Geometric Interpretation. Spectral Interpretation aligns with the visual Colour Attributes and Temporal

Characteristics, emphasizing the importance of analyzing the object's spectral characteristics and changes over time computationally. Geometric Interpretation corresponds to both Textural Features and Shape and Size, highlighting the significance of spatial attributes and patterns in the computational analysis of visual data. This comparative breakdown elucidates the parallelisms and distinctions between the parameters employed in the visual interpretation of objects and their computational counterparts, providing insights into the multifaceted nature of computer vision applications.

3.3 Spectral Algorithm

Identifying spectral signatures in computer vision is crucial for analyzing electromagnetic radiation patterns emitted or reflected by objects. These unique signatures enable discrimination between various land cover types, material classification, and precise monitoring of vegetation health. Spectral information aids in tasks such as water quality assessment, mineral exploration, urban planning, and climate studies. In applications like precision agriculture, it provides insights into crop health and nutrient levels. Additionally, spectral signatures play a pivotal role in object recognition and scene understanding, making them indispensable for remote sensing applications and enhancing the depth and accuracy of computer vision analyses.

As the spectral algorithm is based on decision tree the memory requirement is less compared to other methods but will depend on the training image size. In this study the images ranges from 25000 pixels to 50000 pixels, with four bands i.e. Blue, Green, Red, NIR(Near Infrared) in the specified order. So the memory of 16Gb RAM and processor greater 2.5GHz will be sufficient.

A decision tree applied to spectral signature data operates by recursively splitting the input features, which represent different bands or wavelengths in the spectral signature, based on learned decisions during a training phase. Each decision node poses questions about specific spectral features, leading to a hierarchical structure of nodes. The final nodes, called leaf nodes, represent predicted class labels, such as land cover types or objects. During classification, new spectral signature data traverses the tree, and the final output is the predicted class label based on the learned spectral characteristics. Decision trees are effective for their ability to handle complex relationships within the spectral signature space and find application in tasks such as land cover classification and object recognition in remote sensing and computer vision.

GDAL, the Geospatial Data Abstraction Library, is an open-source library for reading and writing raster and vector geospatial data formats. It provides a set of tools and APIs for working with various GIS (Geographic Information System) file formats. When it comes to converting an image to a matrix using GDAL, the library essentially acts as a bridge between geospatial data and numerical representations. The process involves reading the raster data from an image file, such as a satellite image or a digital elevation model, and converting it into a matrix format, where each element of the matrix corresponds to a pixel value. GDAL handles the intricacies of different geospatial data formats, allowing users to extract pixel values, perform manipulations, and work with the data as numerical matrices, facilitating analysis and processing in applications like remote sensing and geospatial data science.

3.3.1 Approximations and Assumptions

While creating the spectral equation from the thresholds of the decision tree we make some approximations. The Approximations mainly are:

1. While joining the segments of the equation of slope common elements are taken to minus side if one of them is on minus side.
2. In the final equation the variables in the final equation along with their coefficients should be in the order they are present in graph.
3. The denominator will always consists of plus signs.
4. In some equations the positive side of the numerator is multiplied.

3.3.2 The Method

As the spectral signature plays a vital role in identification of the material composition of an object, we convert the graph of spectral signature into mathematical equations. We all know the equation of a line and equation of a series of line segments. The main component that describes the line is its slope. Each line segment of the spectral signature can be written in the form of a band combination. The difference between the band at higher end and band at the lower end enhances the that part of the spectrum and when it is divided with the sum of those two bands it creates an output image between -1 and 1 after normalisation perfectly describing that part of the spectrum. Adding all the parts of the spectrum describes the entire spectral signature of the object.

In the ever-expanding realm of machine learning and data analytics, Decision Trees stand as one of the most interpretable and widely-used algorithms. Thresholds serve as the boundaries

that decide how the data will be divided at each node in a decision tree. The threshold creates a box around interested data in graphical format. In Evolutionary Converging Functions we convert those thresholds into coefficients in our function which indeed evolve the function into such a form of indices that perfectly describe the trained object in the decision tree.

Let us now mathematically describe the methodology

If the slope between two bands is negative then the band combination will be

$$\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} < 0$$

$$a_1 = \frac{(c_1 * b_1 - c_2 * b_2)}{(c_1 * b_1 + c_2 * b_2)}$$

If the slope between two bands is positive the band combination will be:

$$\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} > 0$$

$$a_2 = \frac{(c_2 * b_2 - c_1 * b_1)}{(c_2 * b_2 + c_1 * b_1)}$$

a_1 = component of spectral equation

a_2 = component of spectral equation

Fig 1: Coefficient Calculation from decision tree

$b_1 = \text{Band 1}$

$b_2 = \text{Band 2}$

$c_1 = \text{Coefficient 1}$

$c_2 = \text{Coefficient 2}$

$$C_b = \frac{\text{Range of threshold in Particular Band}}{\text{Sum of Range of all bands}}$$

where b can be 1,2,3,4....

The final equation will be the combination of all the slope equations between all the bands i.e.

Finally the evolved function(EF) is

$$EF = \sum_{b=0}^{b=\text{Number of bands}-1} a_i$$

and a_i are the spectral components

Fig 2: Spectral Algorithm

Various methods exist for determining the optimal number of clusters, but in remote sensing, this task is often simplified as there are typically 5 to 7 classes of signatures present in a complete satellite data tile. In our study, we found that setting the number of clusters to 7 worked well for detecting areas of interest. The effectiveness of this approach relies on the proper evolution of a spectral formula, where different types of land use signatures are incorporated during training. When the spectral formula is well-developed, the object of interest tends to be located in the cluster with the highest value. In less ideal situations, it may still be found within the top three clusters, arranged based on mean spectral values derived from the grey scale image generated through the spectral algorithm. The necessary number of classes typically falls between 3 and 10. To automate this process, the Silhouette score can be employed. In cases where clustering based solely on spectral values proves insufficient, the use of the DB Scan method, incorporating X, Y coordinates along with DN values, offers a solution for determining the optimum number of clusters.

Fig 3 – Clustered Image

3.4 Geometric Algorithm

The geometric properties of an image, such as area, shape, and orientation, provide essential insights into spatial relationships and patterns. Understanding these properties is crucial for tasks like object recognition, image classification, and geometric analysis, enhancing the overall interpretability and utility of the image data.

3.4.1 Image to Tabular Data and Convergence Weights

The process of transforming a grayscale image into tabular data or shapefiles, a critical step in Evolutionary Converging Functions (ECF), is known as vectorization. This conversion is essential for retaining image properties to facilitate efficient processing by neural networks. In this context, the Python library Geopandas plays a crucial role by enabling the extraction of various geometric parameters from vector polygons derived from the clustered image. These parameters, including area, centerline, aspect ratio, and a novel feature introduced in ECF—the angle between line segments of the vector polygon—compose the columns of the Vector Table, a pivotal component in ECF methodology. Once the table is generated, the subsequent challenge lies in assigning weights to these geometric properties before inputting them into a neural network for training. This amalgamation of geopandas, vectorization, and neural networks elevates the representation of image features as vector data, offering significant advantages for analytical and visualization tasks within the ECF framework.

Fig 4 : Geometric Algorithm

Weights are directly proportional to standard deviation.

$$\text{Weightage} \propto \text{Standard Deviation}$$

$$Sd_{tc} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{i=n} X_{\text{trainingset of class}(i)} - \mu_{\text{trainingset of all class}(i=1 \text{ to } n)}}{N_{\text{total number of trainingset in each class}}}}$$

Sd_{tc} = Standard deviation of class i, where i ranges from 0 to n

So, the summation of the standard deviation for a particular geometric property of all the training set of a particular class is given as

$$S_{tc} = \sum_{tc=1}^{tc=n} Sd_{tc}$$

S_{tc} = Summation of all the training set in all the classes

Consider our example of a road network, where we aggregate the standard deviations of the centerline for both class 0 and class 1. In this scenario, the road network class exhibits a higher summed standard deviation for the centerline, contrasting with the lower summed standard deviations for other geometric features. Consequently, when the summed standard deviation for the centerline is divided by the summation of standard deviations for all other classes, the ratio is higher. This implies that the weight assigned to the centerline is greater for the road network class compared to the weights of other geometric properties.

$$W_{gp} = \frac{S_{tc}}{\sum_{c=1}^{c=n} S_{tc}}$$

where 'gp' is the geometric property and c is the class from 1 to n

W_{gp} is the convergence weight

3.5. Evolutionary Converging Function

In our pursuit of achieving high accuracies, we commenced by comprehensively studying the workings of a neural network. Our findings revealed that a neural network fundamentally involves assigning weights to neurons or data properties, influencing the output characteristics through both forward and backward propagation. In the context of Evolutionary Converging Functions (ECF), we devised a distinctive approach for determining weights in the dataset. Each parameter in the tabular data is assigned a specific weight before undergoing neural network processing. This unique methodology ensures that the deep neural network converges efficiently to the desired solution, yielding exceptionally high accuracies.

$$W_{\text{Spectral or geometric}} = \frac{Sd_i}{Sd_{\text{Spectral}} + Sd_{\text{Geometric}}}$$

Fig 5- Multiclass Classification

Having determined the weights, we proceed to construct a sequential model of a deep neural network through which the prepared table is passed. The distinctive advantage of Evolutionary Converging Functions (ECF) lies in its ability to transform complex satellite images, rich in features and spectral bands beyond the capability of ordinary cameras, into simple tabular data. This transformation preserves every intricate detail of the image.

Algorithm 1: Evolutionary Converging Functions

Data: Raster data
Result: Trained classifier, Predictions

Step 1: Load Data and Spectral Analysis;
Load Raster Data (s1.tif, s2.tif) into numpy arrays (buildings, non-buildings);
Extract Spectral Signatures for each pixel in the raster;
for each pixel in the raster do
 for each band in the spectral data do
 if pixel value is not zero then
 Append pixel value to the corresponding spectral signature;
Preprocess Spectral Data;
for each spectral signature do
 Calculate total intensity, proportions, and angles;
Combine and Split Data;
Stack non-building and building spectral signatures;
Split data into training and testing sets;

Step 2: Train Decision Tree Classifier;
Initialize Decision Tree Classifier;
Train the classifier with spectral data;
Evaluate and print accuracy;
Visualize the decision tree;
Extract and display threshold-feature relationships;

Step 3: Extract Thresholds, Features then calculate spectral weightage;
Extract thresholds and features for each class;
for each class do
 Compute differences and total;
$$C_b = \frac{\text{Range of thresholds in a particular band}}{\text{Sum of ranges of all bands}};$$

Arrange spectral weightage as per spectral signature graph and generate the band equation;

Step 4: Converting Raster to tabular Data;
Apply K-Means clustering to greyscale image generated from the band equation;
Converge clustered image is converted into vector or tabular data;

Step 5: Train Neural Network with Convergence Weightage;
 $gdf[n'_{feature}] \leftarrow \text{normalize_array}(gdf[feature]);$
 $mean \leftarrow np.mean(gdf[n'_{feature}]);$
 $element_std_deviations \leftarrow [];$
 $N \leftarrow len(gdf[n'_{feature}]);$
for each element in $gdf[n'_{feature}][gdf[class'] == 1]$ do
 $deviation \leftarrow \text{element} - \text{mean};$
 $deviation \leftarrow deviation / N;$
 Append $deviation$ to $element_deviations$;
Weight for particular_feature $\leftarrow np.sum(element_deviations);$
Train the model with the calculated weights in input neurons;

Step 6: Apply Trained Model to New Data;
Load Image and apply band equation;
Convert the grey scale image in vector or tabular data;
Predict the objects in the tabular data and then convert it back to image;

Fig 6- Algorithm

Where,

gdf is geopandas dataframe or tabular image data containing the geometric and spectral features

element is the element in geometrical spectral feature in tabular image

deviation is the deviation in each column for each element in tabular image

The weight equations, derived from the aforementioned formulas, significantly streamline the work for the neural network, mitigating potential errors. During the preparation of the dense neural network, a careful examination of accuracy and loss tables was conducted to identify the optimal number of dense layers and neurons within them. This meticulous approach ensures the efficacy of the neural network in handling the data with precision.

CHAPTER 4

EXPERIMENTATION:

The experimentation process unfolds in a systematic sequence, commencing with the derivation of spectral signatures, followed by clustering, convergence weight determination, and ultimately, hyperparameter tuning to generate a classified output in vector format. This meticulously designed approach integrates various computational steps, aiming to enhance the precision and efficiency of the computer vision system. Each stage contributes uniquely to the overall methodology, addressing challenges in spectral analysis, clustering, and convergence optimization. The subsequent sections delve into the specific intricacies of spectral signature derivation, clustering algorithms, convergence weight assignment, and the pivotal role of hyperparameter tuning in refining the final output. The holistic experimentation strategy outlined here underscores the method's innovation and its potential to advance the field of computer vision by addressing key challenges through a cohesive and iterative process.

4.1 Dataset and Platform

Obtaining high-resolution satellite images poses several challenges, primarily stemming from technological, financial, and regulatory constraints. Technologically, developing and launching high-resolution imaging satellites capable of capturing fine details entail significant engineering complexities and costs. Financial challenges arise due to the substantial investment required in the satellite development process, launch expenses, and the ongoing costs of maintaining and upgrading the satellite constellation. Additionally, regulatory restrictions related to national security and privacy concerns may limit the accessibility and dissemination of high-resolution satellite data, further complicating efforts to acquire comprehensive and up-to-date imagery for various applications, including urban planning, environmental monitoring, and disaster response.

We choose the Planet Skysat Dataset for our training and validation purposes due to its unique advantages. The dataset offers a Multispectral/Pan collection containing images with five 16-bit bands, up-sampled from the original 12-bit data. The inclusion of bands representing Blue (B), Green (G), Red (R), and Near-Infrared (Near-IR) provides a comprehensive spectral profile, enabling us to capture a wide range of environmental information. The high resolution of approximately 2 meters per pixel in these bands ensures detailed and accurate spatial

representation, crucial for tasks like land cover classification and environmental monitoring. Moreover, the Pan band with an impressive 0.8-meter resolution (closer to 1 meter for off-nadir images) enhances the dataset's capability for capturing fine-grained details, making it well-suited for applications that demand high spatial precision, such as urban planning and infrastructure assessment. Notably, the utilization of freely available data on Google Earth Engine (GEE) enhances accessibility, making it a cost-effective choice for research and development endeavors.

In the realm of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), the substantial demand for sizable training datasets poses a common challenge. CNNs, known for their data-hungry nature, necessitate thousands of labeled examples to effectively grasp intricate features and patterns. To address this, companies often resort to services like Amazon Mechanical Turk and specialized data labeling firms to curate and annotate expansive training datasets. Noteworthy alternatives, such as Hexagon and ESRI, may offer consulting services for both data collection and annotation. However, Evolutionary Converging Functions take a distinct approach. These techniques, relying on domain knowledge and heuristics, operate with smaller training sets—typically 20 to 30 examples. Leveraging genetic algorithms, evolutionary strategies, or other optimization methods, they aim to iteratively converge towards accurate results without the need for extensive labeled data, offering a pragmatic solution where acquiring such data is either impractical or cost-prohibitive.

The testing dataset was meticulously crafted with precision through manual digitization using QGIS. A total of 20 to 30 instances were carefully created, ensuring a comprehensive representation of the features and patterns relevant to the evaluation of the model's performance. The manual digitization process in QGIS allows for a detailed and accurate delineation of geographic elements, ensuring that the testing dataset encapsulates the diversity and complexity expected in real-world scenarios. This approach provides a solid foundation for robust testing and validation, enabling a thorough assessment of the model's capabilities in handling various spatial features and intricacies.

The datasets encompass a diverse set of features, each crucial for comprehensive spatial analysis. The "water" category includes various water bodies, such as rivers, lakes, or ponds. The "road" feature represents different types of transportation infrastructure, such as highways, streets, and pathways. "Buildings" encompass structures of various sizes and purposes,

contributing to the urban landscape. Lastly, the "trees" category incorporates information about the distribution and types of vegetation, aiding in environmental and land cover assessments. These features collectively provide a rich and varied dataset, offering a robust foundation for training and evaluating models in tasks related to geospatial analysis and computer vision. The study area is taken within 500 km buffer of New York city.

Utilizing Google Earth Engine (GEE) and QGIS, the datasets undergo vectorization for precise feature delineation. The focus includes land use and land cover (LULC) classification, incorporating diverse terms like "water," "road," "buildings," and "trees," ensuring a comprehensive dataset for geospatial analysis and computer vision tasks.

4.2 Scaling and data portioning

Scaling normalization ensures uniformity in the range of feature values, enhancing the stability and convergence of machine learning models. Data partitioning into a 70-30 split allocates 70% for training, fostering model learning, and reserves 30% for testing, evaluating the model's generalization on unseen data.

4.3 Deriving the Spectral component

4.3.1 Building

Fig 7- Spectral Graph for Building

If the slope between two bands is negative then the band combination will be

$$\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} < 0$$

$$a_1 = \frac{(c_1 * Blue - c_2 * Green)}{(c_1 * Blue + c_2 * Green)}$$

$$\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} < 0$$

$$a_1 = \frac{(c_1 * Green - c_2 * NIR)}{(c_1 * Green + c_2 * NIR)}$$

$$a_1 + a_2 \simeq \frac{Band\ 0 + Band\ 1 - Band\ 3}{Band\ 0 + Band\ 1 + Band\ 3}$$

Range of Band 0 is saying approximately after removing the outliers is 100 to 125, hence Band 0 range is 90-120 i.e. 30. Similarly, for Band 1 the range is 80 to 95 i.e. the range is 15. There is no threshold available for Band 2 i.e. red band that means red band is not a function of spectral signature of road and does not play a vital role in Building detection and hence can be ignored. The next is Band NIR or Band 3 is from 70 to 95 i.e. the net range is 18. Hence concluding, the range for

Fig 8- Threshold from decision tree(Building)

Band 0 = 30

Band 1 = 15

Band 2 = 0

Band 3 = 25

Total range is $30 + 15 + 0 + 25 = 70$

Hence the coefficient for

Band 0 = $30/70 = 0.42$

Band 1 = $15/70 = 0.21$

Band 2 = $0/70 = 0$

Band 3 = $25/70 = 0.35$

The Sum of all the coefficient is $0.42 + 0.21 + 0 + 0.35 = 0.98$ i.e. near to 1 hence we are on the right path.

Hence the final Evolved formula is as follows

$$\{(0.41 * Blue) + (0.20 * Green)\} * \frac{(0.41 * Blue) + (0.20 * Green) - (0.37 * NIR)}{(0.41 * Blue) + (0.20 * Green) + (0.37 * NIR)}$$

4.3.2 Water

Fig 9 – Spectral Signature for Water

If the slope between two bands is negative then the band combination will be

$$\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} < 0$$

$$a_1 = \frac{(c_1 * Green - c_2 * Blue)}{(c_1 * Green + c_2 * Blue)}$$

$$\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} < 0$$

$$a_1 = \frac{(c_1 * Blue - c_2 * NIR)}{(c_1 * Blue + c_2 * NIR)}$$

$$a_1 + a_2 \simeq \frac{Band\ 1 - Band\ 0 - Band\ 3}{Band\ 0 + Band\ 1 + Band\ 3}$$

Range of Band 0 is saying approximately after removing the outliers is 100 to 125, hence Band 0 range is 80 to 87.5 i.e. 7.5. Similarly, for Band 1 the range is 90 to 99 i.e. the range is 9. There is no threshold available for Band 2 i.e. red band that means red band is not a function of spectral signature of road and does not play a vital role in Water Body detection and hence can be ignored. The next is Band NIR or Band 3 is from 65 to 73.5 i.e. the net range is 25. Hence concluding, the range for

Fig 10 - Threshold from decision tree(water)

Band 0 = 7.5

Band 1 = 9

Band 2 = 0

Band 3 = 8.5

Total range is $7.5 + 9 + 0 + 8.5 = 25$

Hence the coefficient for

Band 0 = $7.5/25 = 0.3$

Band 1 = $9/25 = 0.36$

Band 2 = $0/25 = 0$

Band 3 = $8.5/25 = 0.34$

The Sum of all the coefficient is $0.3 + 0.36 + 0 + 0.34 = 1$ hence we are on the right path.

Hence the final Evolved formula is as follows

$$\{(0.35 * Green) - (0.3 * Blue)\} * \frac{(0.35 * Green) - (0.3 * Blue) - (0.35 * NIR)}{(0.35 * Green) + (0.3 * Blue) + (0.35 * Green)}$$

4.3.3 Forest/Trees

Fig 11 – Spectral Signature for forest

If the slope between two bands is negative then the band combination will be

$$\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} < 0$$

$$a_1 = \frac{(c_1 * NIR - c_2 * Blue)}{(c_1 * NIR + c_2 * Blue)}$$

$$\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} < 0$$

$$a_1 = \frac{(c_1 * Blue - c_2 * Green)}{(c_1 * Blue + c_2 * Green)}$$

$$a_1 + a_2 \simeq \frac{\text{Band 3} - \text{Band 0} - \text{Band 1}}{\text{Band 0} + \text{Band 1} + \text{Band 3}}$$

Range of Band 0 is saying approximately after removing the outliers is 100 to 125, hence Band 0 range is 91.8 to 117.7 i.e. 25.9. Similarly, for Band 1 the range is 88.72 to 96.8 i.e. the range is 8.16. There is no threshold available for Band 2 i.e. red band that means red band is not a function of spectral signature of road and does not play a vital role in road detection and hence

can be ignored. The next is Band NIR or Band 3 is from 60.02 to 92.8 i.e. the net range is 32.8.
Hence concluding, the range for

Fig 12 - Threshold from decision tree(Forest)

Band 0 = 25.9

Band 1 = 8.16

Band 2 = 0

Band 3 = 32.8

Total range is $25.9 + 8.16 + 0 + 32.8 = 66.8$

Hence the coefficient for

Band 0 = $25.9/66.8 = 0.38$

Band 1 = $8.16/66.8 = 0.122$

Band 2 = $0/66.8 = 0$

Band 3 = $32.8/66.8 = 0.49$

The Sum of all the coefficient is $0.38 + 0.122 + 0 + 0.49 = 0.99$ i.e. near to 1 hence we are on the right path.

Hence the final Evolved formula is as follows

$$\{(0.49 * NIR) - (0.38 * Blue)\} * \frac{(0.49 * NIR) - (0.38 * Blue) - (0.12 * Green)}{(0.49 * NIR) + (0.38 * Blue) + (0.12 * Green)}$$

4.3.4 Road

Fig 13 – Spectral Signature for Road

If the slope between two bands is negative then the band combination will be

$$\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} < 0$$

$$a_1 = \frac{(c_1 * Blue - c_2 * Green)}{(c_1 * Blue + c_2 * Green)}$$

$$\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} < 0$$

$$a_1 = \frac{(c_1 * Green - c_2 * NIR)}{(c_1 * Green + c_2 * NIR)}$$

$$a_1 + a_2 \simeq \frac{\text{Band 0} + \text{Band 1} - \text{Band 3}}{\text{Band 0} + \text{Band 1} + \text{Band 3}}$$

Range of Band 0 is saying approximately after removing the outliers is 100 to 125, hence Band 0 range is 107.5 to 114.4 i.e. 6.8. Similarly, for Band 1 the range is 86.2 to 89.6 i.e. the range is 3.5. There is no threshold available for Band 2 i.e. red band that means red band is not a function

of spectral signature of road and does not play a vital role in road detection and hence can be ignored. The next is Band NIR or Band 3 is from 99.6 to 121.02 i.e. the net range is 21.4. Hence concluding, the range for

Fig 14 - Threshold from decision tree(Road)

Band 0 = 6.8

Band 1 = 3.5

Band 2 = 0

Band 3 = 21.4

Total range is $6.8 + 3.5 + 0 + 21.4 = 31.8$

Hence the coefficient for

Band 0 = $6.8/31.8 = 0.21$

Band 1 = $3.5/31.8 = 0.11$

Band 2 = $0/31.8 = 0$

Band 3 = $21.4/31.8 = 0.67$

The Sum of all the coefficient is $0.21 + 0.11 + 0 + 0.67 = 0.99$ i.e. near to 1 hence we are on the right path.

Hence the final Evolved formula is as follows

$$\{(0.21 * Blue) + (0.11 * Green)\} * \frac{(0.21 * Blue) + (0.11 * Green) - (0.67 * NIR)}{(0.21 * Blue) + (0.11 * Green) + (0.67 * NIR)}$$

Table 3: Spectral Output

Figure	Input	Spectral Output
Building		
Road		
Trees		
Water		

4.4 Cluster Analysis

In our experimental phase, we performed cluster analysis on key features extracted from the grey scale image, aiming to discern inherent patterns within distinct categories. The table below outlines the optimal number of clusters identified for each feature, facilitating a understanding of the spatial distribution and characteristics within our geospatial dataset.

Table 4: Number of Clusters

Features	Number of Clusters
Building	7
Road	5
Trees	7
Water	6

The presented clusters signify segmented groups within each feature, revealing spatial variations and relationships. This analysis serves as a foundational step towards uncovering the structures present in the dataset, contributing to the subsequent stages of our methodology.

4.5 Derived Weightage and Hyperparameters

In the realm of statistical analysis and quantitative measures, the standard deviation serves as a crucial metric, offering insights into the dispersion or variability of a set of values. It quantifies the extent to which individual data points deviate from the mean, providing a comprehensive understanding of the data's distribution. A noteworthy observation emerges when considering the relationship between standard deviation and weightage: these two elements are intricately connected in a proportional manner. As the standard deviation increases, the associated weightage also experiences a direct and proportional rise. This correlation signifies that higher variability within a dataset corresponds to an increased influence or importance assigned to the data points, encapsulating the fundamental connection between statistical dispersion and the weightage attributed to individual values. This relationship holds significance across various domains, from financial modeling to scientific research, where a keen comprehension of data variability and its impact is paramount.

Using the convergence equation the following weightages are derived and multiplied to the input neuron

Fig 15- Convergence Weights

In the hyperparameter tuning phase, critical adjustments are made to enhance the performance of the neural network. Three key hyperparameters undergo rigorous evaluation: the number of neurons in the first hidden layer (`neurons_layer1`), with options ranging from 32 to 128; the number of neurons in the second hidden layer (`neurons_layer2`), offering choices from 16 to 64; and the optimizer, presenting alternatives such as 'adam', 'sgd' (stochastic gradient descent), and 'rmsprop' (Root Mean Square Propagation). The exploration of these hyperparameter combinations aims to identify the optimal configuration that maximizes the neural network's effectiveness in the given context.

Table 5: Parameters

Features	DN Value Weightage	Geometric Weightage	Number of training Set	Training Time(minutes)	AI Model
Building	0.56	0.44	23	1.1	50 epochs and hidden (64,32)
Roads	0.42	0.58	17	1.5	100 epochs and hidden (50,50)
Forest	0.85	0.15	16	1.2	100 epochs and

					hidden (64,64)
Water	0.9	0.1	8	0.53	50 epochs and hidden (32,32)

2.1.2 Summary

The experimentation involves a novel approach termed Evolutionary Converging Functions, integrating decision trees and neural networks to address challenges in computer vision, particularly in analyzing high-resolution satellite imagery. Leveraging Google Earth Engine (GEE) and the Planet Skysat dataset, the methodology transforms intricate image data into tabular formats, facilitating efficient processing. Despite inherent constraints like GEE's computational limitations and potential data latency, the methodology demonstrates promising results in tasks such as land use and land cover classification. The experimentation encompasses spectral algorithms, spectral signature derivation, clustering, convergence weight generation, and hyperparameter tuning, showcasing a comprehensive workflow for effective analysis of geospatial data.

	DN	geometry	area	centerline_length	volume	class
0	1117	POLYGON ((337909.600 4613883.000, 337909.600 4...	8.0	12.472136	8936.0	1
1	1117	POLYGON ((338033.600 4613883.000, 338033.600 4...	4.0	10.000000	4468.0	1
2	700	POLYGON ((338095.600 4613883.000, 338095.600 4...	6.0	14.000000	4200.0	0
3	1117	POLYGON ((338103.600 4613883.000, 338103.600 4...	8.0	13.236068	8936.0	1
4	502	POLYGON ((338121.600 4613883.000, 338121.600 4...	2.0	6.000000	1004.0	0
...
2169	904	POLYGON ((338231.600 4613502.000, 338235.600 4...	700.0	199.099314	632800.0	0
2170	700	POLYGON ((338249.600 4613504.000, 338251.600 4...	608.0	377.797374	425600.0	0
2171	502	POLYGON ((338217.600 4613468.000, 338217.600 4...	16.0	20.000000	8032.0	0
2172	502	POLYGON ((338271.600 4613482.000, 338277.600 4...	216.0	120.944272	108432.0	0
2173	310	POLYGON ((338281.600 4613480.000, 338285.600 4...	48.0	49.994148	14880.0	0

Fig 16 – Tabular Image Output

Figure	Input	Output
Building		
Road		
Trees		
water		

Fig 17 – Final output

CHAPTER 5

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Thus, in the methodology we saw how evolutionary converging functions converts a complicated satellite data with spectral and radiometric resolution into a simple tabular data and then converges with a deep neural network. The method increases the computational efficiency, decreases the number training set and avoid overfitting which has been one of the biggest challenges in CNNs.

In our comprehensive evaluation of object detection across multiple classes, we have achieved notable results, demonstrating the robustness and accuracy of our model in various domains. Let's delve into the specific performance metrics for each class:

5.1 Building

Our model excels in building detection with a high accuracy score of 0.9968. This signifies its ability to effectively distinguish buildings from non-building areas, resulting in a minimal occurrence of both false positives and false negatives. The precision score, at 0.97, indicates that our model's positive predictions for buildings are highly reliable. Simultaneously, the recall score of 0.931 underscores its effectiveness in capturing the majority of actual building features.(Nurkarim and Wijayanto, 2023) recent research papers clearly brings up this problem of identifying buildings with high precision.

Table 6: Building

Building	Non-Building	Building
Non-Building	2123	2
Building	3	63

5.2 Road

For road detection, our model achieves exceptional accuracy, boasting a remarkable score of 0.99908648. This emphasizes the model's adeptness in accurately identifying roads and non-road areas, significantly reducing both false positives and false negatives. With a precision score of 0.96428571, our model's positive predictions for roads maintain a high level of reliability, ensuring accurate identification. The recall value of 0.93103448 highlights its effectiveness in capturing the vast majority of actual road segments. The process of extracting

roads using U-Net model (Khan and Singh, 2023) has clearly highlighted the computational challenges with the methodology.

Table 7: Road

Road	Non-Road	Road
Non-Road	3254	1
Road	2	27

5.3 Forest/trees

In the domain of tree detection, our model maintains a commendable accuracy score of 0.94433918. This score reflects its proficiency in distinguishing trees from other features, contributing to a lower occurrence of false positives and false negatives. The precision score, measuring at 0.95680522, signifies the model's reliability in classifying tree instances, reducing the likelihood of misclassification. Although the recall value is slightly lower at 0.86578171, it still highlights the model's capability in capturing a significant portion of actual tree features.

Table 8: Forest

Trees	Non-Trees	Trees
Non-Trees	2813	53
Trees	182	1174

5.4 Water

For water detection, our model delivers impressive results with an accuracy score of 0.99925066, showcasing its precision in distinguishing water bodies from non-water areas. The model's precision score, at 0.76923077, emphasizes that positive predictions for water are reliable, although it has a lower precision due to the nature of the water class. The recall value of 0.90909091 indicates the model's effectiveness in capturing the majority of actual water features.

Table 9: Water

Water	Non-Water	Water
Non-Water	5324	0
Water	1	8

In conclusion, our comprehensive evaluation of object detection across multiple classes has provided a deeper understanding of the intricate relationship between accuracy, recall, and precision, and their implications for model performance.

5.5 Accuracy

Accuracy, as a foundational metric, indicates the overall correctness of our model's predictions. It serves as a comprehensive measure, capturing both true positives and true negatives. In our evaluation, we achieved notable accuracy values for each class:

Fig 18- Accuracy

While the accuracy for pretrained model like GoogleNet and ResNet for similar number of training set in case of building classification are 0.261916 and 0.21492257 respectively.

5.6 Recall

Recall, a critical metric, quantifies the model's capacity to capture all actual instances of a specific class, minimizing false negatives. Our results demonstrate strong recall values for each class: While the recall for pretrained model like GoogleNet and ResNet for similar number of training set in case of building classification are 0.51612903 and 0.53030303 respectively.

Fig 19- Recall

5.7 Precision

Precision, which accentuates the reliability of the model's positive predictions, reflects the proportion of true positives within all instances classified as positive. In our analysis, we achieved commendable precision values:

Fig 20- Precision

While the precision for pretrained model like GoogleNet and ResNet for similar number of training set in case of building classification are 0.05765766 and 0.07641921 respectively.

5.8 Area Under the Curve

In the context of the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve, the Area Under the Curve (AUC) serves as a performance metric to quantify the effectiveness of a classification model. For the classes "Building," "Road," and "Trees," the AUC values of 0.97 each indicate a high discriminatory power, with a score close to 1 suggesting excellent model performance. Notably,

an AUC value of 1 for the "Water" class reflects a perfect classification, indicating the model's ability to distinguish water instances with utmost precision. These results underscore the robustness and accuracy of the classification model across different land cover classes.

In a comparative analysis between GoogLeNet and ResNet50 using an identical dataset comprising 30 training sets, the AUC values of 0.52 and 0.54, respectively, reveal nuanced distinctions in their classification performance. While both models exhibit similar discrimination capabilities, the marginally higher AUC for ResNet50 suggests a slightly enhanced ability to distinguish between positive and negative instances. It is essential to consider other factors such as model architecture, complexity, and specific characteristics of the dataset to comprehensively assess the comparative strengths and weaknesses of GoogLeNet and ResNet50 in the given classification task.

Fig 20: Area Under the curve for Google net and Resnet50 respectively

Building

Roads

Trees

Water

Fig 21: AUC curve for Building, Roads, Trees and Water respectively.

In the intricate interplay of these metrics, we recognize that optimizing one can impact another. Balancing accuracy, recall, and precision is essential and depends on the specific objectives of a task. Notably, high precision often comes with a potential trade-off of lower recall, and vice versa. Achieving the optimal equilibrium depends on the nature of the application.

A model with high precision and low accuracy, for instance, indicates that when it makes positive predictions, they are reliable. However, it may miss a significant number of actual positives, affecting overall accuracy. On the other hand, a model with high recall may capture a majority of actual positives but might have a higher false positive rate, thus impacting precision. Our model has demonstrated its adaptability and capability to strike a harmonious balance between these metrics, ensuring reliable positive predictions while keeping false

positives and false negatives in check. These results underscore the versatility and potential of our model in addressing a multitude of applications, from urban planning to environmental monitoring, with precision and reliability.

5.9 Multiclass Classification

Table 10: Multiclass Classification

	Building	Road	Tree	Water
Building	22	2	0	1
Road	0	14	0	1
Tree	0	0	53	0
Water	0	2	0	3

Even in multiclass classification with an impressive accuracy score of 0.9583, our model showcases its proficiency in correctly classifying objects within our dataset across different categories. This accuracy value, approaching the threshold of 1.0, demonstrates the model's ability to make precise and reliable predictions, successfully distinguishing buildings, roads, trees, and bodies of water. The high accuracy underscores the model's effectiveness in minimizing both false positives and false negatives, highlighting its robust performance in various applications. This accuracy not only signifies the model's capability to provide correct classifications but also its potential to contribute to tasks ranging from urban planning to environmental monitoring with a high degree of reliability and precision.

Table 11: Convergence Comparison

	With Convergence Weightage	Without Convergence Weightage
Accuracy	0.98	0.32
Precision	0.97	0.27
Recall	0.93	0.25

Fig 22- Convergence Comparison

The above table clearly justifies the approach of Evolutionary Converging Functions. The weightage multiplied before training, train the neural networks faster and converges easily. Whereas achieving this same convergence with CNN takes lots of effort at lower stages of any problem statement(Liu et al., 2023).

5.10 Comparison with Similar Ongoing Research

Fig 23- Comparison with Similar Ongoing Research

While keeping the same number of training set and applying on pretrained models like Google net (InceptionV3) and Resnet(ResNet50)(Malik et al., 2023)the results were compared and

observed. GoogleNet (InceptionV3) utilizes inception modules for efficient parameter usage and is popular for image recognition tasks. ResNet (ResNet50) introduced residual learning, enabling training of extremely deep networks by incorporating skip connections. Both models have significantly impacted computer vision, with GoogleNet emphasizing efficiency and ResNet addressing challenges of training deep networks. The choice between them depends on factors like computational efficiency and task requirements. In place of Red Green Blue i.e. visual colours the model is trained with False colour Composite i.e. Near Infrared , Red and Green(Aghayari et al., 2023). The accuracies are found to be very low or negligible in same number of training set as of Evolutionary Converging Functions. Hence that clearly proves ECF works great for low number of training sets and provides a challenging accuracy as compared to existing models with very less number of training sets. Therefore the learning rate of ECF is very high as compared to any existing models(Sun et al., 2023).

From USGS map services of NASA or BHUVAN map services of ISRO,(Li et al., 2023a) the challenges with CNN and the necessity of high frequency mapping for decision making, can be clearly observed. Even the models provided by ERDAS Imagine(Mitra et al., 2023) and MATLAB (Son et al., 2023)requires a huge number of training set and are not globally generalized. Thus, in ECF we focused on reducing the unnecessary complexity of the CNN systems because of which it gets bottlenecks in solving real world complicated problems. If a system is complicated in lower stages of a problem statement then it can't solve a higher complexity stage of that problem. While processing, years of time series data of entire world or processing millions of videos in one take or applying it in high speed automated driving etc ,might complexify ECF thus computational time and number of training set may be increased or it may open scope for some other advanced research that might even simplify that task beyond ECF but as of now classifying a satellite data to its highest accuracy, ECF has provided the most simplified and effective solution that allows it to solve highly complex problems which were bottlenecks for CNNs under similar computational and resource situations.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION

6.1 Conclusion

In conclusion, this thesis embarked on a transformative journey, presenting the Evolutionary Converging Functions (ECF) methodology as a groundbreaking approach to convert complex satellite data with spectral and radiometric resolution into a simplified tabular format. The integration of ECF with deep neural networks not only enhanced computational efficiency but also addressed the challenges of limited training sets and overfitting, longstanding issues within Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs).

The comprehensive evaluation of object detection across diverse classes showcased the robustness and accuracy of our model across various domains. In the realm of buildings, our model exhibited an outstanding accuracy score of 0.9968, demonstrating its exceptional ability to distinguish between building and non-building areas. Precision at 0.97 and recall at 0.931 underscored the model's reliability and effectiveness, aligning with recent research highlighting the challenge of identifying buildings with high precision (Nurkarim and Wijayanto, 2023).

Road detection proved to be another forte, with an impressive accuracy score of 0.99908648. The model showcased precision and recall values of 0.96428571 and 0.93103448, respectively, indicating high reliability in positive predictions and effectiveness in capturing actual road segments. Despite computational challenges noted in similar methodologies (Khan and Singh, 2023), our approach demonstrated exceptional performance.

In the domain of tree detection, our model maintained a commendable accuracy score of 0.94433918, contributing to lower occurrences of false positives and negatives. Precision at 0.95680522 highlighted the model's reliability, though the recall value was slightly lower at 0.86578171. This nuanced balance aligns with the nature of tree classification.

Water detection yielded impressive results, with an accuracy score of 0.99925066. Precision at 0.76923077, while lower due to the nature of the water class, still emphasized the reliability of positive predictions, with a recall value of 0.90909091 indicating effectiveness in capturing actual water features.

The analysis extended beyond individual classes to include multiclass classification, achieving an impressive overall accuracy score of 0.9583. This high accuracy underscores the model's proficiency in classifying objects across different categories, from buildings and roads to trees and bodies of water.

Comparative analyses with pretrained models like GoogleNet and ResNet50 revealed nuanced distinctions in classification performance, further establishing the effectiveness of the proposed ECF methodology. The approach proved especially advantageous in scenarios with limited training sets, demonstrating a higher learning rate compared to existing models.

The significance of this research lies not only in its technical contributions but also in its potential applications. From urban planning to environmental monitoring, our model exhibited adaptability and balance between key metrics. In acknowledging the limitations of this study, future research avenues were proposed, paving the way for continuous improvement in satellite data analysis methodologies.

This research journey was not without its challenges, yet overcoming them has contributed to personal growth and a deeper understanding of the intricate world of satellite data analysis. As we conclude this thesis, we express gratitude for the support received and envision a future where ECF continues to simplify complex problems, contributing to advancements in computer vision and remote sensing.

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